

**ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE
DETERMINATION OF ZENOXACIN BY UFLC IN TOPICAL SEMISOLID
DOSAGE FORMS**

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Abstract:

Ozenoxacin ointments are available in the market. Ozenoxacin is a novel topical, non-fluorinated quinolone antimicrobial agent. The literature review reveals that there is no official monograph for Ozenoxacin ointment in Indian Pharmacopoeia and also no analytical method reported for the analysis of Ozenoxacin ointments in topical semi solid dosage form by UFLC. Spectrophotometer and RP-HPLC are the reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form.

Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical method development for the determination of ozenoxacin by UFLC in topical semi solid dosage forms. Present work is aimed to develop a new, simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible analytical method development and validation for the determination of ozenoxacin by UFLC in topical semi solid dosage forms. The developed method will be validated according to ICH guidelines, Q2. Retention time of Ozenoxacin was found to be 2.717 minutes. The %RSD of nine accuracy samples of Ozenoxacin found between 99.0 to 100.90. The system precision is 0.55 %, Intermediate precision for day 01 is 0.77% and the intermediate precision for Day 02 is 0.62%. So the method developed was simple and economical with less analytical time and less solvent usage. And can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

Key words: Ozenoxacin ointments, RP-HPLC, UFLC

1.Introduction :

Ozenoxacin ointments are available in the market. Ozenoxacin is a novel topical, non-fluorinated quinolone antimicrobial^{1,5}. Ozenoxacin Cream 1% w/w was approved by United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in December 2017 to treat Impetigo caused by Staphylococcus aureus or Streptococcus pyogenes in pediatric patients with two months of age and older as well as adults¹². Ozenoxacin belongs to the quinolone group of antimicrobials and is the first non-fluorinated quinolone, which has a pyridinyl group at C7^{3,5}.

The literature review reveals that there is no official monograph for Ozenoxacin ointment in Indian Pharmacopoeia and also no analytical method reported for the analysis of Ozenoxacin ointments in topical semi solid dosage form by UFLC. Spectrophotometer and RP-HPLC are the reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form⁷⁻¹³.

Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical method development for the determination of ozenoxacin by UFLC in topical semi solid dosage forms. Present work is aimed to develop a new, simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible analytical method development and validation for the determination of ozenoxacin by UFLC in topical semi solid dosage forms. The developed method will be validated according to ICH guidelines, Q2⁶.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials:

Ozenoxacin ointments prepared in house, HPLC grade water, Acetonitrile, Trifluoroacetic acid. All the above chemicals and solvents are from Rankem.

2.2. Instruments:

- Electronics Balance-Mettler
- pH meter –Hanna, 5 Point calibration
- UltraSonicator-BVK enterprises
- LC-20AD PROMINENCE UFLC
- SOFTWARE:LC SOLUTION SHIMADZU

2.3. METHODS:

Chromatographic condition:

1. Column: Thermo C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 3microns
2. Wave length:235nm
3. Flow rate:0.7ml/min
4. Injection volume:2 μ l
5. Mobile phase: Mixture of solution A: Solution B (650:350)
Solution A --Water: Trifluoroacetic acid (1000:0.5)
Solution B-- Water: Trifluoroacetic acid: Acetonitrile (20:0.5:980)

2.3.1. Diluent: Based up on the solubility of the drugs, diluent was selected, mobile phase used as diluent.

2.3.2. Preparation of Standard solution: Weigh accurately and transfer about 10 mg of Ozenoxacin standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with mobile phase. Further transfer 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase.

2.3.3. Preparation of Sample solution: Weigh accurately equivalent to 10mg of Ozenoxacin into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve by sonicating for 30 minutes and makeup to the volume with mobile phase. Further take 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase

3. Validation:

3.1. System suitability parameters: The system suitability parameters were determined by injecting standard solution of Ozenoxacin at the nominal concentration for five times and the percentage RSD for Area and Retention times are calculated⁴.

3.2. Specificity⁷: Checking of the interference in the optimized method. No interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of Ozenoxacin should observed in this method.

3.3. Precision⁵:

3.3.1. Preparation of standard solution: Weigh accurately and transfer about 10 mg of Ozenoxacin standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with mobile phase. Further take 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase.

3.3.2. Preparation of sample solution: Weigh accurately equivalent to 10mg of Ozenoxacin into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve by sonicating for 30 minutes and makeup to the

volume with mobile phase. Further take 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase.

3.3. Linearity ⁶:

3.3.1. Preparation of standard stock solution: Weighed accurately and transferred about 10mg of Ozenoxacin standard into 200 ml volumetric standard flask.

3.3.2. 50% Ozenoxacin Standard solution: 5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50 ml.

3.3.3. 75% Ozenoxacin Standard solution: 7.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50 ml.

3.3.4. 100% Ozenoxacin Standard solution: 10ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50 ml.

3.3.5. 125% Ozenoxacin Standard solution: 12.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

3.3.6. 150% Ozenoxacin Standard solution: 15ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

3.4. Accuracy⁶:

3.4.1. Preparation of Standard stock solution: Weigh accurately and transfer about 10 mg of Ozenoxacin standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase. Transfer 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase.

3.4.2. For preparation of 80% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer sample equivalent to about 8 mg of Ozenoxacin into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase. Transfer 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase. Three independent samples prepared and analysed as per the test method.

3.4.3. For preparation of 100% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer sample equivalent to about 10 mg of Ozenoxacin into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase. Transfer 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase. Three independent samples prepared and analysed as per the test method.

3.4.4. For preparation of 120% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer sample equivalent to about 12 mg of Ozenoxacin into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with mobile phase. Transfer 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase. Three independent samples prepared and analysed as per the test method.

Procedure:

The standard solution, Accuracy -80%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -120% solutions were injected. The amount of Ozenoxacin was calculated and the results were summarized.

3.5. Robustness6: Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate and Wavelength were made and six samples were analysed.

4.Results&discusstion:

4.1.Wavelength detection

10 µg/ml solution of Ozenoxacin at UV region from 200-800nm. The wavelength detected was found to be 235nm.

Fig:1.UV SPECTRA

4.2.Method development: Method development was done by changing various, mobile phase ratios, buffers etc.

Trial 1:**Chromatographic conditions:**

Mobile phase	: Solution A: water (500:500)
Flow rate	:0.7ml/min
Column	:INERTSIL ODS C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 3 μ
Detector wave length	:235nm
Injection volume	:2 μ L
Run time	:5 min
Diluent	: mobile phase

Results

:Improper system suitability

condition.

Fig.2.Trial chromatogram**Trial 2:****Chromatographic conditions:**

Mobile phase	: Solution B: Acetonitrile (400:500)
Flow rate	:0.7ml/min
Column	:Phenomenex,C18 (50 mm X 3 mm, 3 μ m)
Detector wave length	:235nm
Injection volume	:2 μ L
Run time	: 12 min

Diluent : Methanol

Results : improper peak elution so, further trialis carried out.

Fig.3. Trial chromatogram 2

Trial 3:**Chromatographic conditions:****Mobile phase** : Solution A : Solution B (400:600)**Flow rate** :0.7ml/min**Column** : INERTSIL ODS C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 3 μ **Detector wave length** : 235nm**Injection volume** :2 μ L**Run time** :15 min**Diluent** :Mobile phase& methanol**Results** :improper peak elution and more run time so, further trial is carried out.**Fig.4.Trial chromatogram 3**

Optimized conditions (Trail 4)

Chromatographic conditions:

Mobile phase	: Solution A: Solution B (650:350)
Flow rate	:0.7ml/min
Column	:Thermo C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 3microns
Detector wave length	:235nm
Injection volume	:2 μ L
Run time	:6 min
Diluent	: mobile phase
Results	: Retention time and peak shape is good.

Fig.5.Optimized Chromatogram

Observation: Ozenoxacin was eluted at 2.717 minutes. The percentage RSD for five replicate injections of standard solution was well within the limit, so this method was optimized and to be validated.

4.3. System suitability: All the system suitability parameters were within the range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines.

System suitability parameter for Ozenoxacin

Sample ID	Ozenoxacin	
	RT	AREA
Injection -01	2.728	457886
Injection -02	2.710	457412
Injection -03	2.708	458412
Injection -04	2.715	457563
Injection -05	2.722	456985
Average:	2.717	457651
SD:	0.01	534
% RSD:	0.31	0.12

Table.No.1. System suitability parameter for Ozenoxacin

Discussion: The percentage RSD for area and retention time of five replicate standard solution were 0.12 and 0.31 respectively. All the system suitable parameters were passed and were within the limit of less than 2.0%..

5. Validation:

5.1. SPECIFICITY:

Specificity for Ozenoxacin

Sample ID	Ozenoxacin	
	RT	AREA
BLANK	2.717	No peak observed
STANDARD	2.717	457651
PLACEBO	2.717	No peak observed

Table.No.2.Specificity for Ozenoxacin**Fig.7.Chromatogram of placebo**

Fig.8. Typical Chromatogram

Discussion: Retention time of Ozenoxacin was eluted at 2.717min. We did not find any interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention time of Ozenoxacin in this method. So, this method was said to be specific.

5.2. Linearity:

6.3 Linearity data of ozenoxacin

Discussion: Five linear concentrations of Ozenoxacin were injected and linearity equations obtained for Ozenoxacin $y = 0.0000x + 0.4112$. Correlation coefficient (R^2) obtained was 0.9999.

5.3.Precision:

5.3.1. SYSTEM PRECISION:The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for All six injections in UFLC. The % RSD of the six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits

System precision of Ozenoxacin

Conc. Level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in mg)	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample -01	1002.32	452367	0.994	99.40
	Sample -02	1012.35	456326	0.993	99.30
	Sample -03	1005.84	458756	1.005	100.50
	Sample -04	1003.68	457854	1.005	100.50
	Sample -05	1008.65	455897	0.996	99.60
	Sample -06	1005.86	457563	1.002	100.20
	Average :			0.999	99.92
	SD. :			0.005	0.549
	% RSD :			0.5	0.55

Table.No.3.System precision of Ozenoxacin

Tab no. 6.4 System precision of Ozenoxacin

Discussion: The standard solutions was injected for six times as per the test method The percentage RSD for the content of Ozenoxacin was calculated for the samples and found 0.55 which is less than 2.0 and meets the requirements.

5.3.2. INTERMEDIATE PRECISION DAY-01:Multiple sampling from a sample stock solution was done and six working sample solutions of same concentrations were prepared, each injection from each working sample solution was given and obtained areas were mentioned in the table

Conc. level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in mg)	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample -01	1004.23	458754	1.0023	100.23
	Sample -02	1001.52	457563	1.0024	100.24
	Sample -03	1000.98	460153	1.0086	100.86
	Sample -04	1001.87	452136	0.9901	99.01
	Sample -05	1002.87	461236	1.0090	100.90
	Sample -06	1008.65	458754	0.9979	99.79
Average :				1.002	100.17
SD. :				0.007	0.708
% RSD :				0.7	0.71

Table.No.4. Intermediate precision day-01for OZENOXACIN

Discussion:Six independent samples were prepared and analysed as per the test method .The percentage RSD for the content of Ozenoxacin was calculated for the samples and found 0.62 which is less than 2.0 and meets the requirements

5.3.3. INTERMEDIATE PRECISION DAY-02:

Conc. level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in mg)	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample -01	1003.65	453265	1.0093	100.93
	Sample -02	1004.75	452135	1.0057	100.57
	Sample -03	1003.87	450854	1.0038	100.38
	Sample -04	1002.54	444965	0.9920	99.20
	Sample -05	1001.23	448796	1.0018	100.18
	Sample -06	1002.36	447156	0.9970	99.70
Average :				1.002	100.16
SD. :				0.006	0.623
% RSD :				0.6	0.62

Table.No.5.INTERMEDIATE PRECISION DAY-02

Discussion: Six independent samples were prepared and analysed as per the test method. The percentage RSD for the content of Ozenoxacin was calculated for the samples and found 0.62 which is less than 2.0 and meets the requirements.

5.4. ACCURACY:

Accuracy of Ozenoxacin

Sample ID	Sample wt (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Content (in mg)	Calculated Content (in %)
80% sample -01:	800.35	331581	1.009	100.90
80% sample -02:	800.74	379156	1.002	100.20
80% sample -03:	802.98	378125	0.997	99.70
100% sample -01:	1000.35	475500	1.006	100.60
100% sample -02:	1001.56	475486	1.005	100.50
100% sample -03:	1002.58	472156	0.997	99.70
120% sample -01:	1200.57	553799	0.994	99.40
120% sample -02:	1201.37	559864	1.004	100.40
120% sample -03:	1202.36	552458	0.990	99.00
Average :				100.04
SD :				0.627
% RSD :				0.63

Table.No.6.Accuracy of Ozenoxacin

Discussion: Three levels of Accuracy samples in triplicates were prepared and analysed as per the test method. The assay percentage were calculated for the each samples and found the minimum assay is 99.0 and the maximum assay percentage is 100.90 which are well within the limit of 98.0 to 102.0.

5.5. ROBUSTNESS:

S.No	Condition	%RSD of Ozenoxacin Assay
1	Flow rate (-) _0.6	0.41%
2	Flow rate (+) _0.8	0.57%
3	Wavelength (-)_234	0.46%
4	Wavelength (+)_236	0.45%

Table.No.7. Robustness for Ozenoxacin

Discussion: Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.6ml/min), Flow plus (0.8ml/min), Wavelength minus and Wavelength plus was maintained and six samples were injected. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD for the assay values are found to be less than 2.0 which is well within the limit

5.6. ASSAY:

VALIDATION PARAMETER : ASSAY										
LABEL CLAIM:										
OZENOXACIN			1	%						
%w/w			100							
STANDARD DILUTIONS :										
<i>Name of standard :</i> OZENOXACIN										
<i>Purity of standard :</i>			99.30	% (as such)						
25.72	mg diluted to		25	ml, further		1	ml diluted to		100	ml.
SAMPLE DILUTIONS :										
1010.32	mg diluted to		100	ml, further		1	ml diluted to		10	ml.
STANDARD VALUES :										
457886	457412	458412	457563	456985						
Average : 457652										
SD : 534.501										
% RSD : 0.12										
SAMPLE VALUES :										
452365	457125									
Average : 454745.000										
SD : 3365.83										
% RSD : 0.74										
Content in mg										
454745	X	$\frac{25.72}{25}$	X	$\frac{1}{100}$	X	$\frac{100}{1010.32}$	X	$\frac{10}{1}$	X	$\frac{99.30}{100.00}$ X 100.00
=		1.005 mg								
Content in %										
<i>Limit :</i>			98	%		to	102	%		
=		100.50 %								

Table.No.8.ASSAY

Assay: Assay was performed with the above formulation. Average percentage Assay for Ozenoxacin 100.50%.

6. Conclusion:

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the estimation of the Ozenoxacin in semi solid dosage form. Retention time of Ozenoxacin was found to be 2.717 minutes. The %RSD of nine accuracy samples of Ozenoxacin found between 99.0 to 100.90. The percentage RSD of six samples in method precision was 0.55. and the Intermediate precision results are also well within the limit as in the above table.

So the method developed was simple and economical with less analytical time and less solvent usage. And can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

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